

Comparison of Levobupivacaine and Levobupivacaine with Dexmedetomidine in Infraumbilical Surgeries under Spinal Anaesthesia

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Received: 25-08-2024 / Revised: 23-09-2024 / Accepted: 26-10-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Spinal anesthesia is a popular choice for infraumbilical surgeries due to its effectiveness and minimal systemic effects. Levobupivacaine, a long-acting local anesthetic with lower cardiotoxicity than bupivacaine, is commonly used. Combining it with adjuvants like dexmedetomidine, an alpha-2 adrenergic agonist, may enhance analgesia and prolong the effects of anesthesia.

Methods: This randomized double-blind study involved 120 patients undergoing elective infraumbilical surgeries. Participants were divided into two groups: Group L received 0.5% levobupivacaine, and Group LD received levobupivacaine with dexmedetomidine. Outcomes such as onset and duration of sensory and motor blocks, hemodynamic stability, and postoperative analgesia were assessed.

Results: The onset of sensory block was significantly faster in Group LD compared to Group L, with times of 5.40 ± 0.79 minutes versus 6.80 ± 1.37 minutes, respectively ($P < 0.001$). Similarly, the duration of the sensory block was markedly longer in Group LD, lasting 306.18 ± 10.60 minutes compared to 179.55 ± 7.16 minutes in Group L ($P < 0.001$). For motor block onset, Group LD experienced a quicker onset at 7.02 ± 1.19 minutes, compared to 13.10 ± 2.12 minutes in Group L ($P < 0.001$). The duration of the motor block was also prolonged in Group LD, with a duration of 199.22 ± 9.76 minutes, compared to 145.75 ± 8.25 minutes in Group L ($P < 0.001$).

Conclusion: The addition of dexmedetomidine to levobupivacaine for spinal anesthesia improves the onset and duration of anesthesia and provides better postoperative analgesia compared to levobupivacaine alone. This combination may enhance patient outcomes in infraumbilical surgeries.

Keywords: Levobupivacaine, Bupivacaine, dexmedetomidine, Sensory effect, Motor effect.

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Introduction

Spinal anaesthesia is a widely used technique for infraumbilical surgeries due to its simplicity, cost-effectiveness, and ability to provide effective analgesia with minimal systemic effects.

Levobupivacaine, a long-acting local anaesthetic, has emerged as a safer alternative to bupivacaine because of its reduced cardiotoxicity and neurotoxicity. Its effectiveness in providing reliable sensory and motor blockade makes it a popular choice for regional anaesthesia in lower abdominal and lower limb surgeries. However, achieving prolonged analgesia and stable hemodynamic conditions in these procedures remains a challenge. [1]

To enhance the quality and duration of spinal anaesthesia, adjuvants are commonly used in combination with local anaesthetics. Dexmedetomidine, a highly selective alpha-2 adrenergic agonist, has gained attention as a potential adjuvant due to its sedative, analgesic,

and anxiolytic properties. When added to local anaesthetics like levobupivacaine, dexmedetomidine has been shown to prolong the duration of sensory and motor blockade, while also improving postoperative analgesia without significantly increasing adverse effects.

The addition of dexmedetomidine may offer an advantage in terms of better patient comfort, prolonged pain relief, and decreased need for postoperative analgesics. [2,3] This study aims to compare the efficacy and safety of levobupivacaine alone versus levobupivacaine combined with dexmedetomidine in patients undergoing infraumbilical surgeries under spinal anaesthesia.

By evaluating parameters such as onset and duration of sensory and motor blockade, hemodynamic stability, and postoperative analgesia, this research seeks to provide insights into the optimal anaesthetic approach for enhancing

patient outcomes in infraumbilical procedures. [4,5]

Materials and Methods

A randomized double-blind study was performed in 120 patients, aged 20–65 years, of either gender, with physical status ASA Classes I and II, scheduled for elective infraumbilical surgeries under spinal anesthesia. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants. Patients were randomly divided into two groups, Group L and Group LD, each consisting of 60 patients. Group L received 3 ml (15 mg) of 0.5% isobaric levobupivacaine with 0.3 ml of normal saline, while Group LD received 3 ml (15 mg) of 0.5% isobaric levobupivacaine plus 0.3 ml (3 µg) of dexmedetomidine.

The total drug volume remained constant at 3.3 ml across both groups to avoid bias. The anesthesiologist administering the intrathecal block was blinded, with the study drugs prepared by another anesthesiologist. Patients who refused the procedure, were pregnant or lactating, or had coagulation/neurological disorders, spinal injuries, previous spine surgeries, spine sepsis, morbid obesity, allergies to the study drugs, or life-threatening diseases were excluded.

The visual analog scale (VAS), ranging from 0 (no pain) to 10 (severe pain), was used to assess analgesia postoperatively for 24 hours. Rescue analgesia was administered if the VAS score exceeded 3. Premedication included intravenous glycopyrrolate (0.02 mg/kg) 45 minutes before surgery and intravenous midazolam (0.04 mg/kg) immediately before the procedure in both groups. Preoperative vital signs, including pulse rate, heart rate, respiratory rate, blood pressure, and oxygen saturation, were recorded. An intravenous line with an 18G intracath was secured, and patients were preloaded with 10 ml/kg of Ringer's lactate over 15–20 minutes.

Spinal anesthesia was performed under sterile conditions in the left decubitus position. The L3-L4 space (or L2-L3 if needed) was located, and 2% lignocaine was used to raise a skin wheal. A 25G or 26G Quincke spinal needle was used, and once cerebrospinal fluid flow was confirmed, the study drug was injected. Oxygen was administered at 5–6 L/min via a face mask. The anesthesiologist recorded intraoperative data and monitored the patient postoperatively until discharge from the anesthesia care unit.

Sensory block was assessed with a 22-gauge blunt hypodermic needle and motor block using the modified Bromage score at specified intervals, from every 2 minutes for the first 10 minutes, up to hourly until 12 hours post-surgery. Hemodynamic responses were continuously monitored.

Bradycardia (heart rate <60 bpm) was treated with intravenous atropine, and hypotension (systolic blood pressure <20% below baseline) was treated with intravenous ephedrine and additional Ringer's lactate as needed. Surgical anesthesia was initiated once the sensory block reached the T10 dermatome. In cases of failed or partial blocks, general anesthesia was administered, and those patients were excluded from the study.

Statistical analysis was performed, with data expressed as means, standard deviations, numbers, and percentages. Nonparametric data were analyzed using Chi-square tests, and intergroup parametric data comparisons were done with unpaired t-tests. A power analysis indicated the study had a power above 95%.

Results

The mean age, sex, weight, ASA grading, duration of surgery, baseline parameters, and quality of surgical analgesia were similar between the two groups, as detailed in Table 1. Likewise, the intraoperative and postoperative mean respiratory rate, systolic blood pressure, diastolic blood pressure, and oxygen saturation were also comparable between the groups.

In Group L, the mean time to achieve a sensory block up to the T10 dermatome was approximately 6.80 ± 1.37 minutes, while in Group LD it was around 5.40 ± 0.79 minutes. The median maximum sensory level reached was T6 dermatome at approximately 13.70 ± 2.17 minutes for Group L and T4 dermatome at about 6.70 ± 0.94 minutes for Group LD. The mean time for regression of the sensory block to T10 dermatome was roughly 86.50 ± 4.98 minutes in Group L and 113.70 ± 5.30 minutes in Group LD. The mean duration of the sensory block, indicated by the time to regression to the S1 dermatome, was about 179.55 ± 7.16 minutes in Group L and 306.18 ± 10.60 minutes in Group LD. All these differences remained statistically highly significant ($P < 0.001$) [Table 2].

The mean maximum motor block, as measured by the modified Bromage score, was 2 in both groups, indicating no statistically significant difference ($P > 0.05$). However, the mean time to achieve maximum motor block was 13.10 ± 2.12 minutes in Group L and 7.02 ± 1.19 minutes in Group LD. Additionally, the mean total duration of motor block was 145.75 ± 8.25 minutes in Group L and 199.22 ± 9.76 minutes in Group LD. Both of these differences were highly significant ($P < 0.001$) [Table 3]. In Group L, an increase in VAS scores was observed at 120 minutes, leading to the first dose of rescue analgesia at approximately 3 hours postoperatively. A subsequent rise in VAS scores was noted at 8 hours, prompting the second dose at 10 hours. The third and fourth doses were

administered at 18 and 24 hours, respectively. In Group LD, VAS scores increased at around 210 minutes, with the first dose of rescue analgesia given at 5 hours postoperatively. The second dose was administered at 12 hours, and the third dose at 21 hours. Postoperative VAS scores at various intervals were significantly lower in Group LD than in Group L, indicating superior analgesia.

The time to request the first dose of rescue analgesia was delayed in Group LD, at 315.42 ± 22.67 minutes, compared to 175.85 ± 11.98 minutes in Group L, with this difference being highly significant ($P < 0.001$).

The mean number of rescue analgesia doses was 3.55 ± 0.45 in Group L and 2.85 ± 0.29 in Group LD, with this difference also being highly significant ($P < 0.001$)[Table 4].

Table 1: Clinico-Demographic parameters of study groups

Parameters	Group L	Group LD	p-value
Age (years)	37.0–45.2	37.2–45.4	0.725
Sex	Male	38	0.31
	Female	22	
Weight distribution (kg)	59.67–72.93	60.93–74.47	0.744
ASA grading (%)	Grade I	54	0.347
	Grade II	46	
Duration of surgery (min)	51.75–63.25	51.3–62.7	0.654
Heart rate (bpm)	73.94–90.38	74.4–90.93	0.875
Systolic blood pressure (mmHg)	115.2–140.8	112.1–137.0	0.294
Diastolic blood pressure (mmHg)	71.28–87.12	70.85–86.6	0.763
Saturation of peripheral oxygen (%)	89.58–109.48	89.55–109.45	0.671
Respiratory rate (/min)	14.43–17.63	14.58–17.82	0.467

Table 2: Comparison of sensory block characteristics between study groups

Measurement	Group L	Group LD	p-value
Mean time to achieve sensory block (T10)	6.80 ± 1.37	5.40 ± 0.79	<0.001
Median maximum sensory level reached	T6 dermatome at 13.70 ± 2.17	T4 dermatome at 6.70 ± 0.94	<0.001
Mean time for regression to T10	86.50 ± 4.98	113.70 ± 5.30	<0.001
Mean duration of sensory block (regression to S1)	179.55 ± 7.16	306.18 ± 10.60	<0.001

Table 3: Comparison of motor block characteristics between study groups

Measure	Group L	Group LD	p-value
Mean Time to Achieve Maximum Motor Block (minutes)	13.10 ± 2.12	7.02 ± 1.19	<0.001
Mean Total Duration of Motor Block (minutes)	145.75 ± 8.25	199.22 ± 9.76	<0.001

Table 4: Visual analog scale score and rescue analgesia in postoperative period

Time	VAS score postoperative period (mean±SD)		p-value	Rescue analgesia (mean±SD)	
	Group L	Group L		Group L	Group LD
90 min	0.000±0.0000	0.000±0.0000		0.000±0.0000	0.000±0.0000
105 min	0.097±0.3078	0.036±0.1795	0.419	0.000±0.0000	0.000±0.0000
120 min	0.790±0.8584	0.421±0.6852	0.072	0.000±0.0000	0.000±0.0000
150 min	1.820±1.5078	0.215±0.4121	<0.0001	0.237±0.4247	0.000±0.0000
180 min	2.940±1.6214	0.750±0.7350	0.000	0.675±0.4857	0.000±0.0000
210 min	2.420±1.2661	1.460±1.0159	0.002	0.125±0.3384	0.000±0.0000
4 h	1.275±0.9113	2.110±0.8806	0.001	0.000±0.0000	0.000±0.0000
5 h	0.000±0.0000	2.320±1.0654	0.000	0.000±0.0000	0.370±0.4867
6 h	0.000±0.0000	1.790±1.3162	0.000	0.000±0.0000	0.645±0.4918
7 h	0.029±0.1864	0.870±0.7827	0.000	0.000±0.0000	0.000±0.0000
8 h	0.420±0.7654	0.062±0.2610	0.020	0.000±0.0000	0.000±0.0000
9 h	2.410±1.2021	0.290±0.6040	0.000	0.227±0.4328	0.000±0.0000
10 h	2.620±1.6354	1.310±0.9460	0.000	0.475±0.5140	0.000±0.0000
11 h	1.110±1.7253	2.710±1.0582	0.000	0.210±0.4055	0.310±0.4637
12 h	0.470±1.2407	2.690±1.8520	0.000	0.105±0.3082	0.625±0.4905

15 h	1.350±1.7348	0.520±1.1240	0.035	0.270±0.4552	0.065±0.2520
18 h	2.580±1.8976	2.850±1.3551	0.490	0.620±0.4851	0.510±0.5090
21 h	1.220±1.4950	1.950±2.0442	0.221	0.180±0.3776	0.475±0.5089
24 h	3.020±1.4667	1.550±1.6901	0.001	0.510±0.5140	0.240±0.4353

Discussion

Regional anesthesia techniques outperform systemic opioids in both analgesic efficacy and fewer adverse effects. Levobupivacaine is favoured for its quick onset, long-lasting sensory block, shorter motor block duration, and reduced cardiac toxicity. Research indicates that adding dexmedetomidine to levobupivacaine enhances analgesia, extends both sensory and motor block durations, and reduces postoperative pain and side effects. [6-8] there was no significant difference in respiratory rate changes between the two groups ($P > 0.05$), supporting earlier findings by Esmoğlu et al. [9] and Basuni and Ezz [10] that dexmedetomidine does not cause respiratory depression. Heart rate changes were similar across groups, with Group LD receiving an average atropine dose of 1.7 mg and Group L 1 mg, aligning with Esmoğlu et al.'s study. Basuni and Ezz reported bradycardia in 3.3% of their patients, whereas 13% experienced it in this study, likely due to a higher levobupivacaine dose of 15 mg versus their 4 mg.

Despite this, heart rate differences between groups were not statistically significant ($P > 0.05$). Adding dexmedetomidine to levobupivacaine did not lead to significant hypotension, consistent with studies by Esmoğlu et al. and Raval and Chaudhary. [11] This combination decreased the onset time of sensory block and extended its duration, findings that match those of Dizman et al. [12] and Sathitkarnmanee T et al. [13] and others. [14,15] The addition did not alter motor block levels but did prolong them, as noted by Esmoğlu et al. Enhanced postoperative analgesia in Group LD resulted in fewer analgesic doses in the first 24 hours, attributed to the synergistic effect of dexmedetomidine and levobupivacaine. This improvement is consistent with the studies of Kim et al., Basuni and Ezz, Eid et al. [16], and Amer et al. Hypotension and bradycardia rates were 10% and 3% for Group L, and 10% and 13% for Group LD, respectively, with no significant differences between groups ($P > 0.05$), as confirmed by Esmoğlu et al. and Amer et al. [17]

Conclusion

Our study concludes that while both groups were effective for surgical anesthesia and maintaining hemodynamic stability, Group LD showed superior outcomes compared to Group L. Specifically, Group LD had a faster onset of both sensory and motor blocks, a longer duration of these blocks, extended postoperative analgesia, and required fewer doses of rescue analgesia.

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